

LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: *Linguistic Typology (yun typos - copy, template, form, trace and logos - word, doctrine) is a field of linguistics that, from a genetic relationship between languages, has a comparative impact on their structural and functional characteristics.*

Keywords: *function, linguistic, languages, on the basis.*

Scientifically, Linguistic Typology is a method of applying different and similar symptoms in languages to groups, templates and types with a dividing path. The task is distinguished by the typology of kura, functional (social linguistics) and storochal (internal construction and composition of the language). Morphological (typological) classification of languages distinguishes amorphous (not found affixes), agglutinative, inflective, polysynthetic languages on the basis of their grammatical form (type). Linguistic Typology, on the other hand, studies the symptoms in these groups of languages as the expression of categories or different structural signs in lexical-semantic, phonological, grammatical and stylistic satxs, and, consequently, the typology specific to each level of the language is differentiated.

Development of language types the reconstruction of languages is the task of historical typology. Within this typology (sometimes meaningfully applied to it), diachronic typology studies structural changes in languages. Comparing the current state of languages refers to synchronic typology. Linguistic Typology is widely associated with the universals of languages.

While Linguistic Typology seeks to find the storochal laws of characteristics in languages, language universals study how these symptoms spread in which languages in the world.

Alisher Navoi's Work "discussion ullugatayn" belongs to Linguistic Typology, in which semantics in genetically different languages, partly phonetics, are compared. Comparative or cho-brick linguistics, which studies two or more languages in the present era, is also based on Linguistic Typology.

linguistics is the science of language, its social nature, function, internal structure, classification, laws of action (activity) of certain languages, historical

progress. According to the purpose, function and so on, there are several areas (areas) of Linguistics: General Linguistics - a field that studies language a human - specific phenomenon in general, the main task of which is the identification and coverage of the most general characteristics characteristic of world languages, private Linguistics-a field that studies certain linguistic features; Applied Linguistics-a field that, lexicography, linguostatistics, transcription, transliteration, etc.) the direction of development of methods of solution; mathematical linguistics, structural linguistic. Such areas as paralinguistics, ethnolinguistics, Psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics study the linguistic features associated with the activities of the speaker (person)in society.

On the basis of criticism of linguistic naturalism, young Grammarians (German scientists A. Leskin, K. Brugman, G. Astxaf, B. Delbryuk, G. Paul and B.) the school was formed, which focused on the study of living languages. Representatives of this school brought the development of comparative linguistics to a new level. To 19. at hindeurop, the main branches of psychology are (Hellenistic, phonology, romanistics, germanistics, Slavic Studies, Celtic Studies, etc.) was completely formed. Developed for hindeuropa languages, the principles of the history of the slope method have also been applied to bařka languages that are not part of this family. The same forms such fields as semitology, Turkology, finugorology, afrikaansism. 20th of linguistics. an important role in its development in the heads was played by the works of Ferdinand de Sossyurnnt, first of all, the "course of General Linguistics" (1916).

Sossyur created the character theory of language, Synchrony and diachrony, internal linguistics, external linguistics, etc. studied problems. F. de Sossyur's ideas are further developed in the schools of linguistic structuralism that appeared later: the Prague linguistic school - functional linguistics, the Copenhagen linguistic circle (glossematics), the Geneva School, the American descriptive (descriptive) linguistics.

USED LITERATURE:

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